

DIFFICULTIES IN TRANSLATION OF LITERARY TERMS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7007187>

Annotation: This article discusses the complexity of literary translation due to the high semantic load of each word of a literary text. The translator has to not just mechanically translate the text, but recreate each line anew, filling it with exactly the meaning that the author wanted to put in, while being maximally adapted for the Russian reader.

Key words: Translation, translation activity, Simultaneous translation proper .

First of all, the difficulties of literary translation are explained by the high semantic load of each word of a literary text. The translator has to not just mechanically translate the text, but recreate each line anew, filling it with exactly the meaning that the author wanted to put in, while being maximally adapted for the Russian reader. The complexity of literary translation is also determined by the different “vision of the world” - the ways of understanding and reflecting it that are specific to the English and Russian languages. These are two European cultures, and they are much closer than, for example, the cultures of Egypt and Russia, but still there are such features in everyday life and society that are difficult to understand for a reader unfamiliar with English culture³.

A brief list of the main difficulties of literary translation in relation to English-Russian literary translation is as follows: Known fundamental differences between English and Russian languages; Domestic and social features of the life of peoples; National phraseological units, phrasal verbs; Wordplay; The need to find a middle ground between interlinear and free translation; Compliance with style, culture and era;

The so-called “false friends of the translator” are words that are similar in spelling or sound in the original language and in the target language, but differ in their meanings.

A huge number (compared to Russian) of ambiguous words;

In a poetic translation to this list are added:

The need for rhyme, tact;

Saving the author's size;

Criteria for a quality literary translation

The French humanist, poet and translator Étienne Dolet (1509-1546) believed that the translator must observe the following five basic principles of translation. To perfectly understand the content of the translated text and the

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intention of the author whom he translates. To be fluent in the language from which he translates, and to have an equally excellent knowledge of the language into which he translates. Avoid the tendency to translate word for word, as this would distort the content of the original and destroy the beauty of its form. Use commonly used forms of speech in translation; Correctly choosing and arranging words, reproduce the general impression made by the original in the appropriate "tonality".

In 1790, in the book "Principles of Translation" by the Englishman A. Tytler, the basic requirements for translation were formulated as follows. The translation must fully convey the ideas of the original. The style and presentation of the translation should be the same as in the original. The translation should be as easy to read as the original work. Although these principles were formulated centuries ago, they are fully relevant.

The question of the degree of closeness of the translation to the original was widely discussed by the translators of antiquity. There is a so-called "Untranslatability Theory". According to this theory, a full-fledged translation from one language to another is generally impossible due to a significant discrepancy between the expressive means of different languages; translation is only a weak and imperfect reflection of the original, giving a very remote idea of it.6 transmission of thoughts expressed in another language. This is all the more true for the Russian language - one of the most developed and richest languages in the world. The practice of translators proves that any work can be fully (adequately) translated into Russian while preserving all the stylistic and other features inherent in this author.

The translator must satisfy a greater number of requirements in order to create a text that fully represents the original in a foreign culture. Among such criteria, of course, one should mention the preservation of as many tropes and figures of speech as possible as an important component of the artistic style of a work. The translation should signal the era in which the original was created. There are cases when a translator needs not only knowledge, but also special skills. The writer often plays with words, and this game can be difficult to recreate. Here is an English joke based on a pun. A man comes to a funeral and asks: I'm late? And in response he hears: Not you, sir. She is. The English word late means both 'late' and 'late'. The hero asks: Am I late? And they answer him: no, the dead man is not you, sir, but she. How to be? In Russian, the game does not work. But the translator got out of the situation: is it all over? "Not for you, sir. For her. Such traps lie in wait for the translator at every turn. It is especially difficult to

convey the speech appearance of the characters. It's good when an old-fashioned gentleman or an eccentric girl speaks - it's easy to imagine how they would speak Russian. It is much more difficult to convey the speech of an Irish peasant in Russian or Odessa jargon in English. Here, losses are inevitable, and the bright coloring of speech inevitably has to be muffled. It is not for nothing that folklore, dialect and slang elements of the language are considered by many to be completely untranslatable⁸.

Means of information design in a literary text

Epithets - are transmitted taking into account their structural and semantic features (simple and complex adjectives; the degree of compliance with the normative semantic agreement with the word being defined; the presence of metaphor, metonymy, synesthesia), taking into account individualization and position in relation to the word being defined and its function;

Comparisons - are transmitted taking into account the structural features, stylistic coloring of the vocabulary included in it;

Metaphors - are transmitted taking into account structural characteristics, taking into account the semantic relations between the figurative and subject plan;

Author's neologisms are transmitted according to the word-formation model existing in the target language, similar to the one used by the author, while preserving the semantics of the word components and stylistic coloring.

Phonetic, morphemic, lexical, syntactic, leitmotif repetitions - are transmitted, if possible, while maintaining the number of repetition components and the very principle of repetition at a given language level;

A play on words based on the ambiguity of a word or the revival of its internal form - in rare cases of the coincidence of the amount of ambiguity of the played word in the original and the translation, both the meaning and the principle of the game are preserved; in other cases, the game is not transmitted, but can be compensated by playing on a word that is different in meaning, which is introduced into the same text;

Irony - for its reproduction in the translation, first of all, the very principle of contrasting collision, comparison of the incomparable "Speaking" names and toponyms is transmitted with the preservation of the semantics of the "speaking" name and the word-formation model typical of the original language, exotic for the target language; The syntactic specificity of the original text - the presence of a contrast of short and long sentences, the rhythm of prose, the

predominance of a coordinating connection, etc. - is transmitted using grammatical correspondences;

Dialectisms - as a rule, are compensated by colloquial vocabulary; jargon, swear words are transmitted using the vocabulary of the language with the same stylistic coloring. Of course, all elements of form and content cannot be reproduced with accuracy. With any translation, the following inevitably happens:

Some part of the material is not recreated and is discarded.

Some part of the material is given not in its own form, but in the form of various substitutions / equivalents.

Material is brought in that is not in the original.

Therefore, the best translations may contain conditional changes compared to the original - and these changes are absolutely necessary if the goal is to create a unity of form and content similar to the original on the material of another language, however, the accuracy of the translation depends on the volume of these changes - and it is the minimum of such changes that implies adequate translation. All translation decisions when translating a literary text are made taking into account the narrow context and the broad context of the entire work. This concerns the choice of variant correspondences and transformations.

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